

CNN performance in genre classification on popular genres from Amazonian region: An analysis in relation to Human evaluation and its implications

Claudio Gomes^{1,2}[0000-0003-3355-4141] and Tsang Ing Ren²[0000-0002-3677-0264]

¹ Group Music COmpUter and Technologies Emergent (COUT-e)
Computer Science Faculty - Federal University of Amapa - Brazil
claudiorogério@unifap.br

² Centro de Informática, Universidade Federal de Pernambuco - Brazil
tir@cin.ufpe.br

Abstract. Music is one of the most useful means of communication for social organization, influencing coexistence, customs, lifestyle and tastes. Noticeable in different musical genres, whether for: dancing, celebrating, resting, helping in moments of loneliness, sadness, etc. This work presents a dataset containing the musical characteristics of the most popular genres from the Amazonia region, from countries of Bolívia, Brazil, Colômbia, Equador, French Guiana, Peru, Dominican Republic, and Venezuela, with 9 popular music genres: andean, brega, carimbó, cúmbia, merengue, pasillo, salsa, vaqueirada, and zouk. This dataset has 22500 samples, 2500 for each genre, segmented in 5 portions of 20 seconds, represented by mel spectrogram. All tracks were acquired by the YouTube or Spotify platform considering viewing rate and sound quality. To evaluate the AMPOP dataset, a custom CNN model was developed for genre classification. Its performance, measured in terms of precision and accuracy, was compared against several state-of-the-art architectures, including MobileNet, ResNet, VGG, EfficientNet, Xception, MobileViT, and MaxViT. Finally, the classification performance of music genre specialists was analyzed based on more than 500 musical evaluations. It was observed that the proposed model significantly outperformed the human experts; however, this difference may be attributed to the inherent subjectivity of human perception as well as the cultural and contextual complexity of the analyzed genres. This highlights the importance of computational approaches to support music genre classification.

Keywords: artificial neural networks · popular music genres · music information retrieval · amazonian region.

1 Introduction

The music industry has been undergoing a profound transformation driven by technological development. Audio streaming service apps like Spotify, SoundCloud, Deezer, among others, have global statistics on listeners' preferences for

globally recognized music genres compared to regional or local music genres [16]. These softwares have various tools and strategies that facilitate new music choices or suggestions, driving their continuous use or necessity, such as music genre classifiers, identification of similarities between different music genres, subjectivity models for music genres, and preset equalization [22]. For economic, marketing, content access speed, and other reasons, most of these models mentioned above contain little information about music genres in microregions [24]. As a result, listeners are influenced towards preferences for international genres.

In this context, the appreciation of popular music in various countries has gained prominence with the use of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, which drive cultural preservation, reinvention, and dissemination. In China, for example, AI is used to digitize and reinterpret folk songs, creating modern arrangements that bring new generations closer to ancient traditions [5]. In Nigeria, Machine Learning (ML) is used to classify Nigerian music genres based on musical tracks segments, enhancing the export of Afrobeats and other local styles by analyzing data to reach international audiences and diversify its influence [9].

The scarcity of categorized data in musical databases from diverse regions remains a persistent challenge; however, it also reflects and supports cultural diversity and the interplay between local and global musical influences. Moreover, it plays a crucial role in documenting and preserving the rich cultural heritage of these regions for future generations, while enabling the analysis of evolving sonic trends over time.

Amazonia musical genres characterized by their distinctive beats and vibrant rhythms have influenced popular music worldwide, thereby enriching contemporary musical landscapes. This cultural interplay highlights both the universality and the global significance of amazonian contributions to music. However, the classification of lesser known musical genres presents several challenges, including the scarcity of labeled datasets, the structural heterogeneity of sound profiles, and the inherent complexity involved in capturing their unique musical attributes.

This work presents the AMPOP a new dataset from popular music genres from Amazonia region. The AMPOP was created containing popular music genres from Amazonia region from the countries: Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, French Guiana, Peru, Dominican Republic, and Venezuela, considering the main popular musical genres: andean, brega, carimbó, cumbia, merengue, pasillo, salsa, vaqueirada and zouk. After, the dataset was evaluated by AI CNN model to classify these popular music genres. Finally, it was added survey results from musicians experts that classify these genres.

2 Related works

The development of musical databases has become increasingly crucial in the effort to highlight music from regions traditionally underrepresented in the global music landscape. This initiative seeks not only to diversify the datasets avail-

able for artificial intelligence research but also to recognize and preserve musical traditions that are frequently marginalized by dominant industry forces.

As AI tools continue to advance, there is growing awareness of the need to mitigate biases in recommendation systems and genre classification models, which often favor western centric styles and cultural norms. Expanding collections to include music from underrepresented regions enriches the data ecosystem and paves the way for more inclusive models capable of capturing a broader spectrum of sonic characteristics, instrumental textures, musical forms, and sociocultural narratives [28].

Furthermore, this approach carries significant sociocultural implications. By documenting and analyzing music from underrepresented communities, such datasets contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage that is often at risk of erasure. Increasingly, collaborative initiatives involving local researchers, musicians, and technologists are being established that to ensure these musical traditions are captured with authenticity and cultural sensitivity. By highlighting music from geographically and culturally isolated regions, these initiatives contribute to diversity, equitable, and enriched musical landscape within the context of artificial intelligence.

The GTZAN dataset is one of the most widely used public datasets for research in automatic music genre recognition. It contains 1,000 audio tracks, each 30 seconds long, balanced across 10 musical genres: blues, classical, country, disco, hip hop, jazz, metal, pop, reggae, and rock [25]. However, the GTZAN presents several important limitations, including duplicate tracks, labeling errors, and distortions in some recordings, which may affect the evaluation and comparison of music classification systems.

The LAMA dataset is a collection focused on the classification of global music genres. It comprises audio files in WAV format extracted from YouTube videos, organized into four geographical categories: Latin America, Asia, the Middle Eastern, and Africa [15]. In addition to the original files, the dataset includes unbalanced 1-minute audio samples, as well as training data based on Mel-Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs) and graphical representations such as FFTs, STFTs, and waveforms.

LYRA is an audio-visual dataset dedicated to traditional and popular Greek music. It includes metadata annotations such as genre, instrumentation, title, source, region, and geographical coordinates. This study examined the relationships between regions by analyzing musical representations in conjunction with genres and instruments [21].

PMG-Data is a Persian music genre classification dataset built using CNNs [7]. The dataset contains 500 music tracks from five stratified genres. PMG-Data includes metadata such as genre, title, and spectrogram. The tracks were segmented into six parts of 8 seconds each, totaling 3,000 samples, in an attempt to improve accuracy. However, it achieved only 65% accuracy, as the 8-second segments did not provide sufficient information for proper genre identification, limiting the model's learning capacity.

Model	Size	Genres	Time	Input	*BL
Chen[5]	5000	5	Full	MFCC	Yes
GTZAN	1000	10	30s	Audio	Yes
LAMA	2267	4	60s	Audio/AF	No
LYRA	1570	5/32	10s	Mel	No
PMG-DATA	3000	5	8s	Audio	Yes
AMPOP	22500	9	20s	Mel	Yes

Table 1: Related datasets.*BL: Balanced;*AF: Acoustic features vector means;
*NI: Not Informed.

Genres	Raw	Time (h)
<i>Andean</i>	Youtube/Spotify	20.61 / 10.65
<i>Brega</i>	Youtube/Spotify	20.75 / 08.07
<i>Carimbó</i>	Youtube/Spotify	09.20 / 20.34
<i>Cumbia</i>	Youtube/Spotify	25.60 / 05.89
<i>Merengue</i>	Youtube/Spotify	22.25 / 14.79
<i>Pasillo</i>	Youtube/Spotify	13.08 / 14.53
<i>Salsa</i>	Youtube/Spotify	24.80 / 17.61
<i>Vaqueirada</i>	Youtube/Spotify	14.62 / 19.92
<i>Zouk</i>	Youtube/Spotify	18.85 / 16.47
Total	169,76 / 128,27	298,03

Table 2: Raw hours from audio tracks on Ampop dataset.

Table 1 presents a summary of related works together with the AMPOP dataset. It can be observed that AMPOP presents a larger sampling per genre compared to other datasets, representing greater variety in information with the perspective of improving robustness in training and accuracy in computational models. Furthermore, it is noted that some datasets are not balanced, which can create a negative bias for classification generalization and accuracy.

3 AMPOP

This case study presents a Music Information Retrieval (MIR) dataset based on audio segments from popular genres native to the Amazonian region, converging countries such as Bolivia, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, French Guiana, the Dominican Republic, and Venezuela, as shown in Figure 1. The selected genres include andean, brega, carimbó, cumbia, merengue, pasillo, salsa, vaqueirada, and zouk, each representing culturally significant musical expressions within their respective regions. The next subsection presents these genres and their particularities.

Fig. 1: Case Study of Popular Music Genres in the Amazonian Region

3.1 Particularities of popular music genres

Andean music represents a traditional genre of the indigenous peoples of the Andes mountain range, characterized by the use of instruments such as the charango, quena, and zampona, which produce introspective melodies deeply intertwined with cosmological and natural symbolism [4]. Rooted in ancestral cultures of countries such as Peru, Bolivia, and Ecuador, Andean music traces its origins to pre-Columbian traditions and continues to serve as a source of inspiration for contemporary artists [26].

The brega music genre is characterized by romantic lyrics and engaging melodies, often combining elements of tropical rhythms with electric guitars and keyboards with indigenous influences. Popular in the northeast and, particularly, in northern Brazil, it is a symbol of local culture and a style that has entertained parties and generations [1]. Carimbó is a traditional musical genre from the Amazonia region, in the state of Pará, characterized by its vibrant percussion, wooden drums, and circular dances with sensual movements. Originating from indigenous, African, and European influences, carimbó was recognized as Intangible Cultural Heritage of Brazil by IPHAN in 2014 [3], [12].

Originally a coastal cultural expression, cumbia spread throughout Latin America, gaining local variations and becoming a symbol of popular music on the continent [14]. Cumbia is a traditional musical genre and dance originating from Colombia, combining African, indigenous, and Spanish influences, marked by vibrant and percussive rhythms [23].

Merengue is a musical genre from the Dominican Republic, with fast rhythms, use of tambora, güira, and accordion, reflecting African, European, and Caribbean influences [13]. It has big variations in Venezuela and Mexico, becoming a symbol that has gained worldwide popularity due to its contagious energy [11].

Pasillo is a traditional musical genre originated in the Andean region, particularly prominent in Ecuador and Colombia. Characterized by smooth, and

nostalgic melodies, it reflects a syncretic musical form that integrates European influences most notably the waltz with local cultural and stylistic elements. Usually performed with guitar, mandolin, and other acoustic instruments, it is considered a symbol of Andean cultural identity [2] [27].

Salsa is a musical genre and dance with Caribbean roots, especially Cuban and Puerto Rican, that combines Afro-Cuban rhythms, jazz, and Latin music in energetic arrangements. Emerging in the 1960s in New York, it became a cultural movement and symbol of identity for the Latin diaspora [17].

Vaqueirada from northern Brazil is a cultural expression that adapts elements of northeastern tradition to Amazonian influences, celebrating rural life and the universe of cowboys in events that include music, dance, and competitions [6].

The musical genre Zouk originated in the Caribbean islands, particularly in Guadeloupe and Martinique, which are French territories located near French Guiana. Emerging in the 1980s, zouk represents a fusion of traditional Caribbean rhythms, such as Haitian compas, with influences from Afro-Caribbean calypso. The term zouk means “party” in Antillean Creole and is characterized by smooth, engaging beats and a fluid, sensual dance style that reflects Caribbean culture and celebration [19]. Although zouk originated in the French Antilles, its influence extended to nearby regions such as French Guiana and eventually reached Brazil, particularly the north and northeast regions, where it was adapted and mixed with local rhythms [20].

The Amazonia region, known for its great geographical diversity spanning several countries, rich in its fauna, flora, and social ecosystems, also presents music as a great source of wealth and complexity. Whether due to territorial extension or dialects, Amazonian musicality presents totally different proposals, tonalities, and rhythms, with these selected musical genres being icons in local musical production, influencing recent popular genres [10].

Music does not stop with time. These genres show great variation and musical influences, preserving their uniqueness while exploring new musical possibilities. For example, brega incorporates entirely electronic instruments mixed with other musical genres at a faster pace. Both brega and cumbia embrace musical variations; cumbia blends with carimbó, salsa, and electronic music. Carimbó adapts to include traditional instruments like drums and electric guitars [14].

Salsa has been merging with merengue since the 1990s, and Andean pop music blends with cumbia. Vaqueirada incorporates rhythms from carimbó and andean music. In this way, it is evident that this work highlights how the diversity of the Amazon region is linked not only to biodiversity but also to musical and bodily language. Although separated by vast forests, winding rivers, or distinct origins, these genres share common roots with significant local cultural adaptations.

3.2 Dataset construction

The musical dataset consists basically of a computational representation (e.g., mfcc, mel, cqt, tempogram) derived from the content of audio/visual tracks/clips (audio, midi, video) stored in a structured dataset [18].

Fig. 2: Systematic Approach to Dataset Creation and Evaluation

In most cases, a musical audio track exhibits significant structural variations throughout its duration, including elements such as the introduction, chorus, bridge, and ending. As a result, the temporal dynamics of the signal can influence the measurement of various audio features, such as the spectrogram, tonality, tempo (BPM), and sound intensity. Consequently, it is advisable to analyze the track in shorter, segmented intervals rather than relying on a single, full-track evaluation to ensure more accurate and representative feature extraction [8].

Thus, as shown in figure 2, each musical track was segmented into 5 non-overlapping 20 second segments. Preliminary experiments were conducted to evaluate the trade-off between total segment duration and classification accuracy for dataset construction. In this study, all reported results are based exclusively on these 20 second segments for each musical track.

In summary, the dataset illustrated in Figure 2 was preprocessed by converting 20 second segments of the musical tracks into mel spectrogram representations. The audio tracks were sourced from the streaming platforms *YouTube* and *Spotify*. The libraries *PyTube* and *Spotipy* were employed to download the selected music tracks, followed by conversion to WAV mono format at 22,050 Hz using the *ffmpeg* tool. Subsequently, the audio segments were preprocessed through normalization to a range of 0 to 1024.

The *LibRosa*³ library was used to calculate the mel spectrogram with 224 bands by 672 samples, with *fft*, *window*, and *hop* width of 2048, 1728, 656, respectively. The Mel spectrogram was selected as a representation because it captures all the spectral information that has great potential to identify musical variations in classifications with a lower processing cost [28]. Furthermore, the use of Mel spectrogram is appropriate with the use of CNN's and ViT's models that can extract features as spectrogram image references.

Musical tracks exceeding 5,000 views and exhibiting acceptable audio quality were selected, while recordings containing noise, silence, or live performances were excluded. The dataset encompasses over 423 artists, with recordings spanning from 1947 to the present, thereby reflecting both the historical continuity and variability of the selected genres. All tracks were assessed and validated by experts to ensure accurate classification within each musical category.

The primary objective of this study was to classify the selected musical genres, with an emphasis on achieving maximum accuracy across computational models. To this end, the dataset was partitioned into training, validation, and test subsets, comprising 70%, 15%, and 15% of the data, respectively. Given that

³ *LibRosa*: <https://librosa.org/doc/latest/index.html>

Fig. 3: AMPOP CNN architecture. *F: Filters; *K: Kernel; *S: Size.

the dataset comprises five 20 second segments from each musical track, as illustrated in Figure 2, all segments from a single track were assigned to the same subset training, validation, or test during random selection.

This dataset contains mel spectrograms derived from 20 second segments of publicly available music recordings sourced from YouTube and Spotify. The data derived are shared solely for academic research purposes under fair use and with appropriate citation. The dataset is provided exclusively for academic and non-commercial use, with the aim of promoting research in music information retrieval and computational musicology. No content is included that allows for the reconstruction of the original recordings. The dataset is available via a link⁴.

3.3 AMPOP CNN genre classifier

Table 3 reports the validation and test classification outcomes for the dataset, obtained using the optimal optimizer across the AMPOP, EfficientNet, MobileNet, ResNet, VGG16, Xception, MobileViT, and MaxViT architectures. Additionally, the corresponding accuracy, precision, and the hyperparameters selected during the training and validation phases are reported.

<i>Model</i>	ATE(s)	ICR(MB)	Valid(%)		Test(%)		Opt
			Acc	Prec	Acc	Prec	
<i>EfficientNet</i>	355	7988.38	81.34	81.42	77.88	78.59	adam
<i>MobileNet</i>	218	6392.76	85.08	85.13	72.15	72.25	adamax
<i>ResNet</i>	679	46118.58	84.28	84.19	79.38	80.27	adam
<i>VGG</i>	1355	28804.76	91.36	91.48	83.42	83.78	adam
<i>Xception</i>	679	40895.71	94.89	95.02	86.95	87.45	rmsprop
<i>MobileViT</i>	459	34212.08	12.50	12.43	12.50	12.43	adam
<i>MaxViT</i>	3577	26787.42	13.92	13.88	15.08	06.12	rmsprop
AMPOP	221	219.51	96.77	97.48	87.21	87.43	lion

Table 3: Evaluation results on validation and test datasets. Acc: Accuracy; Prec: Precision; *ATE: Average Time by Epoch; *ICR: Initial Computational Resources.

⁴ AMPOP dataset: <https://github.com/claudio-rogerio/AMPOP>

Fig. 4: Test Results with the AMPOP Model

Systematic analyses were conducted on variations in hyperparameters and optimizers. While the model architectures remained constant across configurations, the resulting accuracy and precision exhibited substantial variation depending on the optimizer applied. Based on the results presented in Table 3, all corresponding hyperparameters were held constant to conduct a final evaluation on the test dataset and assess the resulting accuracy and precision.

A strategy was focused on maximizing accuracy and precision, for all models. A batch size was of 256, with optimizer variations as Adam, Adamax, AdamW, LION, Nadam, RMSProp, and SGD. Training was configured with a maximum of 200 epochs, with *early stopping* and an initial learning rate of 0.001, subject to an exponential decay of 80% every 40 epochs.

The AMPOP model was observed to achieve the highest accuracy and precision on the test set, followed by Xception, which yielded the second best performance. However, it is important to highlight that AMPOP has demonstrated a lower Average Time per Epoch (ATE), measured in seconds, and reduced Initial Computational Resource consumption (ICR), measured in MB in training set, eliminating the need for high-performance computing infrastructure. Consequently, AMPOP emerges as the most suitable architecture for the classification of popular music genres from the Amazonian region, a conclusion supported not only by its superior accuracy and precision but also by its lower computational

cost during training and enhanced efficiency during deployment when compared to the other evaluated models.

Regarding audio segmentation, Figure 4 illustrates the evaluation results of the AMPOP model for each audio segment in the dataset, accompanied by a summary of accuracy and precision regarding the classification of individual musical genres. Furthermore, Figure 4a indicate that the classification performance for the *begin* and *end* splits is comparatively less reliable, whereas the *middle* split consistently attains higher accuracy.

As shown in Table 3, MobileViT and MaxViT demonstrated limited generalization capacity. Efforts to enhance performance through modifications such as normalization adjustments, extended training epochs, and increased batch sizes were constrained by computational resource limitations.

4 Survey of classify genres by experts

Given that the genres originate from different countries, as shown in Figure 1, specialists were surveyed using a structured questionnaire to assess their ability to accurately identify the previously mentioned musical genres. Ten musical segments, each consisting of a 30 seconds from the central portion of the track, were randomly presented to the participants, who were asked to determine the genre to which each segment belonged. Figure 5 presents the results of the questionnaire, comprising more than 500 individual evaluations, with an approximate average accuracy of 67%. The Brazilian genres were observed to achieve the highest classification accuracy, while the andean genre showed the lowest performance. It should be noted that the term specialist was defined as an instrumental musician or a computational musician expert, and the survey was conducted exclusively, unfortunately, just with Brazilian participants. The link⁵ is available from the page used for the survey with experts.

Fig. 5: Survey results with experts.

⁵ Index: <https://bit.ly/4leSaAd>

5 Conclusion and future works

A case study was conducted on popular music genres from the Amazonian region, including Andean, Brega, Carimbo, Cumbia, Merengue, Pasillo, Salsa, Vaquerada, and Zouk. Regarding genre classification, the proposed AMPOP model achieved approximately 87.21% accuracy and 87.53% precision.

In addition, based on the classification results provided by expert musicians, a clear difficulty was observed in categorizing these genres, particularly given that they traverse multiple countries with different languages, accents, and musical purposes.

Indeed, the evolution of musical expression, in the principle of creative exploration, frequently involves the integration of novel sonic elements drawn from other musical genres, whether culturally proximate or distant, which are subsequently adapted to contemporary contexts. As a result, many genres incorporate rhythmic, harmonic, or structural features of internationally recognized styles, while simultaneously preserving distinctive regional characteristics.

For future work, a more detailed analysis of acoustic features will be conducted using time-normalized audio samples with durations ranging from 10 to 30 seconds. Furthermore, the dataset will be expanded by increasing the number of samples per genre, in order to improve the robustness and generalization capacity of the classification models.

References

1. Araújo, S.M.: Brega: music and conflict in urban brazil. *Latin American Music Review/Revista de Música Latinoamericana* **9**(1), 50–89 (1988). <https://doi.org/10.2307/779999>
2. Arbeláez, R.E.: La historia del pasillo triste o del pasillo ecuatoriano. *Revista Indisciplinas* **4**(7), 199–211 (2018)
3. Bógea, E.: A cultura no brasil pós-2003, um norte: carimbó patrimônio cultural brasileiro (2014)
4. Brill, M.: The andean region. In: *Music of Latin America and the Caribbean*, pp. 307–353. Routledge (2017). <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315167213>
5. Chen, D., Sun, N., Lee, J.H., Zou, C., Jeon, W.S.: Digital technology in cultural heritage: Construction and evaluation methods of ai-based ethnic music dataset. *Applied Sciences* **14**(23), 10811 (2024)
6. Costa, J.R.D.d.: O boi bumbá de parintins: a evolução da toada numa perspectiva dos ecossistemas de comunicação (2020)
7. Farajzadeh, N., Sadeghzadeh, N., Hashemzadeh, M.: Pmg-net: Persian music genre classification using deep neural networks. *Entertainment Computing* **44**, 100518 (2023)
8. Flexer, A., Grill, T.: The problem of limited inter-rater agreement in modelling music similarity. *Journal of new music research* **45**(3), 239–251 (2016)
9. Folorunso, S.O., Afolabi, S.A., Owodeyi, A.B.: Dissecting the genre of nigerian music with machine learning models. *Journal of King Saud University-Computer and Information Sciences* **34**(8), 6266–6279 (2022)

10. Hidalgo Maldonado, R.S.: Esto es Ecuador: análisis de la fusión pasillo-hip hop dentro del álbum Ecuafornia de la banda Esto es Eso, aplicado a la producción de dos temas inéditos. B.S. thesis, Quito: Universidad de las Américas, 2019 (2019)
11. Horn, D., Feldman, H., Courteau, M.L., Malcomson, H., Narbona Jerez, P.: The Bloomsbury encyclopedia of popular music of the world vol 9. Genres: Caribbean and Latin America, vol. 9. Bloomsbury (2014)
12. Huertas, B.M.: O carimbó: cultura tradicional paraense, patrimônio imaterial do brasil. *Revista cpc* (18), 81–105 (2014)
13. Hutchinson, S.: Merengue típico in transnational Dominican communities: Gender, geography, migration and memory in a traditional music. New York University (2008)
14. Iten, M., Marquez, I.: Digital cumbia: Tradition and postmodernity. *Dancecult: Journal of Electronic Dance Music Culture* **14**(1), 60–75 (2022)
15. Lee, B.W.: LAMA World Music Genre Dataset (2020). <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/13BPFB>, <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/13BPFB>
16. Lindner, J., Felsing, F., Eser, A.: Spotify genre statistics: Pop, rock, and hip-hop dominate preferences (2024), <https://gitnux.org/spotify-genre-statistics/>
17. Lopes, P.D.: Salsiology: Afro-cuban music and the evolution of salsa in new york city. (1993)
18. Maia, L.S., Rocamora, M., Biscainho, L.W., Fuentes, M.: Selective annotation of few data for beat tracking of latin american music using rhythmic features. *Transactions of the International Society for Music Information Retrieval*, vol. 7, no 1, may 2024, pp. 99-112. (2024)
19. Murdoch, H.A.: Zouk and the articulation of french caribbean culture. *Research in African Literatures* **52**(3), 187–222 (2021)
20. Navarro, A.C., Buarque, I., Menegaldo, L.: Tensions of the historiographic traces of brazilian zouk. *Revista Brasileira de Estudos da Presença* **13**, e129684 (2023)
21. Papaioannou, C., Valiantzas, I., Giannakopoulos, T., Kaliakatsos-Papakostas, M., Potamianos, A.: A dataset for greek traditional and folk music: Lyra. In: *Ismir 2022 Hybrid Conference* (2022)
22. Park, M., Thom, J., Mennicken, S., Cramer, H., Macy, M.: Global music streaming data reveal diurnal and seasonal patterns of affective preference. *Nature human behaviour* **3**(3), 230–236 (2019)
23. Party, D.: Troubling gender: Youth and cumbia in argentina’s music scene (2013)
24. Passmore, S., Wood, A.L., Barbieri, C., Shilton, D., Daikoku, H., Atkinson, Q.D., Savage, P.E.: Global musical diversity is largely independent of linguistic and genetic histories. *Nature Communications* **15**(1), 3964 (2024)
25. Sturm, B.L.: The gtzan dataset: Its contents, its faults, their effects on evaluation, and its future use. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1306.1461* (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2014.894533>
26. Tucker, J.: Producing the andean voice: Popular music, folkloric performance, and the possessive investment in indigeneity. *Latin American Music Review* **34**(1), 31–70 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.7560/LAMR34102>
27. Wong, K.: The song of the national soul: Ecuadorian pasillo in the twentieth century. *Latin American Music Review* **32**(1), 59–87 (2011)
28. Zaman, K., Sah, M., Direkoglu, C., Unoki, M.: A survey of audio classification using deep learning. *IEEE Access* (2023)